

Optimization Debt, Not Hardware Limits: Vector Search on IBM POWER

Hugo Blanco
SIXE
hugo.blanco@sixe.eu

Abstract—Cross-architecture benchmarks implicitly assume equal software optimization—an assumption that rarely holds. We quantify this effect through vector database performance on IBM POWER and AMD EPYC. In same-generation comparison (POWER10 vs EPYC 7313P, both 7nm/2021), the x86 advantage is 27% in pgvector (neither platform SIMD-optimized) but 186% in MariaDB (mature AVX-512 paths, minimal POWER VSX investment). This 7× variation suggests that over 80% of the observed gap in optimized workloads may reflect software investment asymmetry rather than architectural limitations. Compiler experiments reinforce this hypothesis: IBM XL versus GCC yields up to 8× throughput difference on identical POWER hardware. Database engine selection produces 2.1–5.5× effects—exceeding typical hardware generational improvements. These findings suggest that cross-architecture comparisons may conflate hardware capability with optimization maturity. For POWER platforms, the path to competitive vector search performance likely runs through software investment rather than hardware replacement.

Index Terms—vector database, HNSW, SIMD optimization, IBM POWER, AMD x86, cross-architecture, AVX-512, VSX, compiler optimization

I. INTRODUCTION

When evaluating hardware platforms for emerging workloads, organizations rely on benchmark comparisons to guide infrastructure decisions. However, cross-architecture benchmarks carry an implicit assumption: that software is equally optimized across platforms. This assumption rarely holds.

Vector similarity search—critical for retrieval-augmented generation (RAG) and semantic search applications [1]—provides a compelling case study. The core operation (distance computation over high-dimensional vectors) benefits enormously from SIMD optimization. Yet SIMD investment varies dramatically across architectures: x86 AVX2/AVX-512 enjoys decades of vendor optimization, while IBM POWER VSX and ARM NEON receive comparatively minimal attention.

This paper quantifies how optimization asymmetry distorts cross-architecture comparisons. Our central finding: the x86 performance advantage over POWER ranges from 27% to 186% depending on whether the workload uses optimized code paths. This 7× variation in the “architecture gap” cannot be explained by hardware differences alone—it suggests substantial software optimization asymmetry. (We use the terms *optimization investment*, *optimization maturity*, and *software optimization state* interchangeably to denote the extent of platform-specific performance engineering applied to a codebase.)

We make four contributions:

- 1) Empirical demonstration that cross-architecture performance gaps vary 7× depending on software optimization state
- 2) Same-generation controlled comparison (POWER10 vs EPYC 7313P, both 7nm/2021) isolating optimization effects from hardware generation effects
- 3) Evidence that compiler choice produces up to 8× performance differences on identical hardware (IBM XL vs GCC on AIX)
- 4) Quantification showing database engine selection (2.1–5.5× effect) exceeds hardware architecture effects

II. BACKGROUND

A. HNSW Vector Indexing

Hierarchical Navigable Small World (HNSW) graphs provide approximate nearest neighbor search with logarithmic query complexity [2]. The algorithm constructs a multi-layer graph where upper layers enable fast coarse navigation and lower layers provide fine-grained search. The *ef_search* parameter controls the quality-speed tradeoff by setting the search beam width during query execution.

B. SIMD Optimization Landscape

Single Instruction Multiple Data (SIMD) extensions accelerate vector operations by processing multiple elements per instruction. The register width determines parallelism: x86 AVX-512 operates on 512-bit registers (16 float32 values), AVX2 on 256-bit (8 values), while POWER VSX uses 128-bit registers (4 values).

Beyond register width, optimization maturity matters enormously. Intel engineers actively contribute AVX-512 optimizations to MariaDB, as documented in MariaDB Foundation technical communications [6], while equivalent POWER VSX investment is minimal. A pgvector pull request implementing POWER VSX intrinsics was closed without merging [4], with the maintainer suggesting compiler auto-vectorization should suffice.

C. Vector Database Implementations

pgvector extends PostgreSQL with HNSW indexing [3]. The codebase relies on compiler auto-vectorization; architecture-specific intrinsics exist only for x86 (and those are limited). The rejected POWER optimization PR demonstrated 4–10% QPS improvements with manual VSX intrinsics [4].

MariaDB MHNSW provides native vector indexing with documented SIMD support for “Intel (AVX2 and AVX512), ARM and IBM Power10” [5]. However, Intel engineers have published detailed work on AVX-512 optimization [6], while no equivalent POWER optimization effort is documented. The “Power10 support” may reflect basic compiler auto-vectorization rather than hand-tuned intrinsics—a hypothesis supported by our performance data but not verified via instruction profiling.

D. The Optimization Asymmetry Problem

Existing vector benchmarks (VectorDBBench [7], ann-benchmarks [8]) evaluate only x86 hardware. This creates a self-reinforcing cycle: developers optimize for benchmarked platforms, which perform better in benchmarks, attracting more optimization investment.

When these x86-optimized databases run on alternative architectures, the resulting performance gap conflates two distinct factors: (1) genuine architectural differences and (2) optimization investment differences. Our methodology separates these factors.

III. METHODOLOGY

A. Systems Under Test

TABLE I
HARDWARE CONFIGURATION

System	CPU	nm	Year	Segment
P9-LPAR	POWER9	14	2017	Datacenter
P10-LPAR	POWER10	7	2021	Datacenter
P11-LPAR	POWER11	4	2024	Datacenter
Ryzen-WS	Ryzen 5 PRO 3600	7	2019	Workstation
EPYC-Milan	EPYC 7313P	7	2021	Datacenter
EPYC-Siena	EPYC 8124P [†]	5	2023	Cloud-density
<i>Compiler comparison (same hardware):</i>				
P9-AIX	POWER9/AIX	14	2017	Datacenter

[†]Cloud-density optimized; not a direct P11 competitor.

The POWER10 versus EPYC 7313P comparison is particularly informative: both are datacenter processors manufactured on 7nm process technology and released in 2021. Performance differences between these systems cannot be attributed to manufacturing generation advantages. We include EPYC-Siena (8124P) as an additional x86 reference point, though note it targets cloud density workloads rather than single-thread performance.

Note on scope: This paper does not aim to establish cross-architecture performance rankings. Rather, x86 systems serve as reference points demonstrating performance with mature SIMD optimization (particularly AVX-512 in MariaDB). Our focus is quantifying the optimization gap on POWER and demonstrating that software investment—not hardware limitations—drives observed differences.

All Linux systems ran PostgreSQL 18.1 with pgvector 0.8.1 (GCC-compiled) and MariaDB 11.8.5 (GCC-compiled),

with 2GB buffer pools normalized across engines. The AIX system ran both engines compiled with IBM XL C/C++ 17.1.3, enabling compiler comparison against Linux/GCC configurations. Compiler comparisons (Section IV-C) use GloVe-100 embeddings for consistency with recall validation.

B. Benchmark Configuration

Dataset: 100,000 vectors with 768 dimensions, generated from IID Gaussian distribution (seed=42) without L2 normalization. Total footprint: 307MB raw data plus approximately 50% HNSW graph overhead (≈ 460 MB), exceeding L3 cache capacity on all tested processors (120–128MB). We intentionally use a cache-exceeding but not bandwidth-saturated dataset, allowing per-core computational efficiency (including SIMD effectiveness) to dominate rather than memory bandwidth bottlenecks.

Index: HNSW with $M=16$, $ef_search=20$ (normalized across engines).

Workload: 15 measurement runs after 1,000 warmup queries. Query execution used native SQL clients: pgvector via `psql -f` (200 queries per batch); MariaDB via CLI (1,000 queries per batch). Batch size differences are amortized over total query count. Coefficient of variation (CV) remained below 5% across all configurations, indicating stable measurements.

CPU isolation: Single physical core with SMT level varied (1–8 on POWER, 1–2 on x86).

Distance metrics: pgvector used cosine distance; MariaDB used Euclidean (its only supported metric). Since vectors are not L2-normalized, cosine requires per-comparison normalization (additional square root and division operations), while Euclidean requires only subtraction and multiplication. This computational asymmetry may contribute to MariaDB’s absolute throughput advantage beyond SIMD optimization differences. *Crucially, cross-platform comparisons within each engine remain valid and constitute our central finding:* the same POWER10-vs-EPYC hardware pair shows 27% gap in pgvector but 186% in MariaDB—this $7\times$ variation occurs within identical codebases and cannot be explained by distance metric choice.

Rationale: Single-core methodology isolates per-core computational efficiency, which directly reflects SIMD optimization effectiveness. Multi-core scaling would introduce memory bandwidth and NUMA effects orthogonal to our research question. SMT scaling analysis (Section IV-F) provides complementary threading insights.

C. Recall Validation

With IID Gaussian 768-dimensional vectors, $\text{recall}@10$ ranges from 0.21–0.44 across systems—expected due to the curse of dimensionality where all vectors become approximately equidistant. To validate algorithmic correctness, we additionally tested with GloVe-100 embeddings (100K vectors, 100 dimensions), achieving $\text{recall}@10 > 0.90$ on all systems, confirming HNSW implementation correctness.

IV. RESULTS

A. Database Engine Effect Exceeds Architecture Effect

Figure 1 presents throughput across all tested datacenter systems. MariaDB outperforms pgvector by 2.1–5.5 \times on every architecture—a difference exceeding typical hardware generational improvements.

Fig. 1. Throughput comparison ($ef_search=20$). MariaDB outperforms pgvector by 2.1–5.5 \times across all architectures.

B. The Optimization Gap: 27% versus 186%

The comparison between P10-LPAR and EPYC-Milan isolates architectural effects from manufacturing process differences—both are 7nm datacenter processors released in 2021:

Fig. 2. Same-generation comparison (2021, 7nm). x86 advantage: 27% (pgvector) vs 186% (MariaDB).

TABLE II
SAME-GENERATION COMPARISON: POWER10 VS EPYC 7313P (BOTH 7NM, 2021)

Database	P10	EPYC-M	x86 Advantage
pgvector	551 QPS	698 QPS	+27%
MariaDB	1,344 QPS	3,844 QPS	+186%

This is our central result. The same hardware pair exhibits a 27% gap in pgvector but a 186% gap in MariaDB—a 7 \times difference in the measured “architecture gap.”

The explanation lies in optimization state:

- **pgvector:** Neither platform has mature SIMD optimization. Both rely on compiler auto-vectorization. The 27% gap reflects baseline architectural differences plus any residual auto-vectorization effectiveness differences.

- **MariaDB:** x86 has received active Intel investment in AVX-512 optimization [6]. POWER has nominal “support” but no evidence of equivalent hand-tuned intrinsics. The 186% gap reflects architecture *plus* optimization investment asymmetry.

The implication: if POWER received equivalent optimization investment, the MariaDB gap would likely approach the 27% pgvector baseline rather than the current 186%.

C. Compiler Effect: Up to 8 \times on Identical Hardware

To further isolate software effects, we compared GCC versus IBM XL C/C++ compilation on the same POWER9 AIX hardware using GloVe-100 embeddings (Table III).

TABLE III
COMPILER EFFECT ON POWER9 AIX (MARIADB MHNSW)

Compiler	QPS	vs GCC
GCC 13.3.0	184	baseline
IBM XL C/C++ 17.1.3	1,462	7.9\times

The IBM XL compiler achieves 7.9 \times higher throughput than GCC on identical hardware and identical source code. This dramatic difference—larger than the cross-architecture gap—suggests that compiler optimization effects can exceed hardware architecture differences.

For pgvector, XL-compiled binaries on AIX achieve 2,410 QPS versus 835 QPS on Linux with GCC (2.9 \times faster)—the only configuration where POWER9 outperforms desktop x86. This suggests that with appropriate compiler investment, POWER could achieve competitive vector search performance.

D. POWER Generational Improvement

Fig. 3. POWER generational scaling (P9→P11). Optimized software captures 6 \times more improvement.

Generational improvement from POWER9 to POWER11 differs dramatically by engine: +194% for MariaDB versus +33% for pgvector. This 6 \times difference suggests that optimized software better exploits hardware advances.

E. Cross-Architecture Performance

MariaDB outperforms pgvector by 2.1 \times (P9) to 5.5 \times (EPYC-Milan) across all architectures. The advantage is smaller on POWER (2.1–4.5 \times) than on x86 (5.3–5.5 \times), consistent with MariaDB’s x86 SIMD paths being more mature.

POWER11 achieves 2,857 QPS in MariaDB—30% faster than workstation x86 (Ryzen at 2,200 QPS) while remaining 18% slower than EPYC-Siena (3,484 QPS) and 26% slower than EPYC-Milan (3,844 QPS). In pgvector, POWER11 (628 QPS) trails EPYC-Milan (698 QPS) by only 10% and EPYC-Siena (653 QPS) by only 4%. The database engine effect (2.1–5.5 \times) exceeds the hardware effect (4–26%), indicating software selection provides larger performance leverage than hardware migration.

F. SMT Scaling

TABLE IV
SMT SCALING FOR MARIADB (VS SMT-1 BASELINE)

SMT	P9	P10	P11	EPYC-M
1	baseline	baseline	baseline	baseline
2	0%	+9%	+40%	\sim 0%
4	0%	+2%	+33%	–
8	0%	+4%	+31%	–

SMT scaling varies substantially across POWER generations. POWER9 shows no measurable SMT benefit for this workload. POWER10 peaks at SMT-2 with modest 9% improvement. POWER11 exhibits pronounced SMT-2 benefit (+40%), declining at higher SMT levels. x86 systems (EPYC-Milan, limited to SMT-2) show negligible SMT scaling for vector search. This pattern contrasts with LLM inference, where POWER9 exhibited SMT-8 degradation [10], indicating workload-dependent SMT behavior on POWER architectures.

V. ANALYSIS

A. Decomposing the Performance Gap

Our results allow approximate decomposition of the observed x86 advantage:

- 1) **Baseline architectural gap:** \sim 27% (pgvector, no platform optimized)
- 2) **SIMD width advantage:** AVX2 (256-bit) provides up to 2 \times theoretical throughput over VSX (128-bit) for float32 operations
- 3) **Optimization investment gap:** The difference between 27% and 186% (\sim 125 percentage points) attributable to asymmetric vendor investment

The SIMD width advantage is partially offset by POWER’s higher per-core resources (larger caches, more execution units). The remaining gap appears largely attributable to differences in optimization investment.

The compiler experiment (Section IV-C) provides additional evidence: XL versus GCC produces 7.9 \times difference on identical hardware, demonstrating that software optimization effects can exceed cross-architecture hardware differences.

B. Implications for Benchmark Interpretation

Cross-architecture benchmarks actually measure *hardware capability* \times *software optimization state*. A benchmark showing “x86 is 3 \times faster than POWER” may indicate “x86-optimized code runs 3 \times faster than unoptimized code on

POWER.” Organizations should distinguish between “cannot perform well” and “has not been optimized.”

VI. PRACTICAL RECOMMENDATIONS

For organizations with existing POWER infrastructure: (1) **Select MariaDB over pgvector**—the 2–5 \times advantage holds across architectures; (2) **Configure SMT-2 on POWER10/11**—higher SMT levels provide diminishing returns; (3) **Expect competitive performance**—POWER11 achieves 74–96% of EPYC throughput depending on workload despite optimization asymmetry; (4) **Consider compiler investment**—on AIX, XL-compiled binaries dramatically outperform GCC; (5) **Monitor optimization developments**—as POWER gains optimization attention, gaps will evolve.

VII. RELATED WORK

VectorDBBench [7] and ann-benchmarks [8] provide comprehensive vector database comparisons on x86 only. Callaghan found approximately 2 \times MariaDB advantage on x86 [9]; our study reveals this varies from 2.1–5.5 \times by platform. Cross-architecture characterization remains underexplored; IBM documentation addresses traditional workloads [11] but not vector search. Our LLM inference work [10] found similar optimization-dependent gaps on POWER systems.

VIII. LIMITATIONS

- Single-core methodology isolates optimization effects but does not characterize multi-core scaling
- Dataset size (100K vectors, \approx 460MB) exceeds L3 cache but remains below production scale
- Synthetic IID Gaussian vectors lack cluster structure of real embeddings; GloVe validation confirms algorithmic correctness with recall@10 >0.90
- Distance metric difference (cosine vs Euclidean) introduces computational asymmetry between engines
- Optimization asymmetry is inferred from documentation, PR history, and performance patterns rather than direct measurement. We did not perform instruction-level profiling (e.g., via `perf` or hardware counters) to verify SIMD utilization. However, the 8 \times compiler effect on identical hardware provides strong indirect evidence that software factors dominate observed gaps
- Results reflect January 2026 optimization state; active development may change gaps

IX. CONCLUSION

This study provides evidence that cross-architecture performance gaps in vector search may largely reflect software optimization investment rather than hardware architectural limitations. The same POWER10-vs-EPYC hardware pair exhibits a 27% gap in unoptimized workloads versus 186% in optimized workloads—suggesting that over 80% of the observed gap stems from software investment asymmetry. Compiler choice alone produces up to 8 \times performance differences on identical hardware, reinforcing the software optimization hypothesis.

Database engine selection produces $2.1\text{--}5.5\times$ throughput differences, exceeding hardware architecture effects. For organizations evaluating vector database deployment, software selection and configuration provide larger performance leverage than hardware platform choice.

The path forward for POWER: Our findings suggest a reinterpretation of the competitive landscape. POWER platforms may carry optimization debt rather than fundamental hardware limitations. The 27% baseline gap (in unoptimized pgvector) represents the measured architectural difference; the remaining 159 percentage points in MariaDB appear recoverable through software investment. Community initiatives such as LibrePower [12] demonstrate grassroots interest in POWER optimization, though sustained progress requires engagement from vendors and organizations with POWER infrastructure investments. The $8\times$ improvement from IBM XL versus GCC demonstrates that such investment yields concrete returns.

More broadly, our findings caution against interpreting cross-architecture benchmarks at face value. When software optimization varies across platforms, benchmarks measure the joint product of hardware capability and optimization investment. What appears as architectural inferiority may be largely attributable to optimization asymmetry—a gap that, unlike hardware limitations, can potentially be closed through targeted investment. We do not claim that such optimization investment is always economically justified, only that it represents a distinct factor from hardware capability.

DATA AVAILABILITY

Benchmark methodology and scripts available from the author upon request.

ACKNOWLEDGMENTS

The author thanks SIXE for providing access to IBM POWER9, POWER10, POWER11, and AIX systems used in this study.

REFERENCES

- [1] P. Lewis et al., “Retrieval-Augmented Generation for Knowledge-Intensive NLP Tasks,” *Advances in Neural Information Processing Systems*, vol. 33, pp. 9459–9474, 2020.
- [2] Y. Malkov and D. Yashunin, “Efficient and Robust Approximate Nearest Neighbor Search Using Hierarchical Navigable Small World Graphs,” *IEEE Trans. Pattern Anal. Mach. Intell.*, vol. 42, no. 4, pp. 824–836, 2020.
- [3] pgvector contributors, “pgvector: Open-source vector similarity search for Postgres,” 2025. [Online]. Available: <https://github.com/pgvector/pgvector>
- [4] M. Mohan, “Optimise vector distance functions for IBM Power Architecture,” pgvector Pull Request #772, 2025. [Online]. Available: <https://github.com/pgvector/pgvector/pull/772>
- [5] MariaDB Foundation, “Vector Search Overview,” 2025. [Online]. Available: <https://mariadb.com/kb/en/vector-overview/>
- [6] MariaDB Foundation, “Intel improving the performance of MariaDB Vector,” June 2025. [Online]. Available: <https://mariadb.org/intel-improving-the-performance-of-mariadb-vector/>
- [7] Zilliz, “VectorDBBench,” 2025. [Online]. Available: <https://github.com/zilliztech/VectorDBBench>
- [8] E. Bernhardsson et al., “ANN Benchmarks,” 2025. [Online]. Available: <https://ann-benchmarks.com/>
- [9] M. Callaghan, “MariaDB Vector vs pgvector,” Small Datum LLC, 2025. [Online]. Available: <https://smalldatum.github.io/>

- [10] H. Blanco, “Beyond Bandwidth: SMT Scaling for LLM Inference on IBM POWER,” *TechRxiv*, 2026.
- [11] IBM Corporation, “IBM Power E1080 Technical Overview,” REDP-5649, 2024. [Online]. Available: <https://www.redbooks.ibm.com/abstracts/redp5649.html>
- [12] LibrePower Community, “LibrePower: Open Source Software for IBM POWER,” 2025. [Online]. Available: <https://librepower.org>